

BUCKLING PROPERTY OF PLAIN WEAVE FABRIC COMPOSITE LAMINATE CONSIDERING INTRALAMINAR INHOMOGENEITY

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials reinforced with woven fabrics are usually used as laminates. When evaluating the mechanical property of the laminate, each lamina is often treated as a homogeneous material. However, the intralaminar inhomogeneity is more significant in woven fabric composites than in unidirectional fiber reinforced composites because yarns are interwoven within each ply and the thickness of each yarn which takes up in the thickness of each ply is relatively large in a woven fabric composite. The intralaminar inhomogeneity may affect the mechanical behavior of the composite laminate, especially the laminate with a small number of laminated plies. In this study, the influence of the variation in the number of laminated plies on the compressive buckling characteristics of plain weave fabric composite laminates was investigated. After the buckling analysis which takes into account the intralaminar inhomogeneity is conducted, the analysis results are verified by experiments. It is found that the reduction of the apparent elastic modulus in the 1-ply lamina or 2-ply laminate due to the effect of the intralaminar inhomogeneity can also cause a reduction of its buckling load.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials such as carbon fiber reinforced plastics are increasingly used in various fields including lightweight structural members in the aerospace engineering field because they are superior in both specific strength and specific stiffness compared to the conventional metal materials. Besides the unidirectional fiber reinforced composite materials, composites reinforced with woven fabrics are also used in the structural members, particularly those with curved surfaces, because of their conformability to the complex shape. These composite materials are usually used as laminated plate or shell (laminate). When evaluating the mechanical properties of these composite laminates, each ply (lamina) is usually treated as the homogeneous material. However, the intralaminar inhomogeneity is more significant in woven fabric composites than in unidirectional fiber reinforced composites because yarns are interwoven within each ply and the thickness of each yarn which takes up in the thickness of each ply is relatively large in woven fabric composites. Yoshida and Nakagami [1] and Yoshida et al. [2] carried out numerical analysis on the elastic properties of woven fabric composite laminates taking intralaminar inhomogeneity into account and reported that the laminate stiffness, particularly the

bending stiffness (apparent bending elastic modulus of the laminate), decreases as the number of laminated plies decreases. Since the bending stiffness is closely related to the buckling property of the laminate, the number of plies included in the laminate may affect the buckling property of the laminate, especially of the laminate with a small number of plies.

In this study, with regard to the plain weave fabric composite laminate, the influence of the variation of apparent elastic moduli with the number of plies included in the laminate on the compressive buckling property of the laminate is investigated through finite element (FE) analysis and experiments. The FE analysis was conducted based on the concept of multi-scale analysis which is shown in Fig.1. The elastic properties used on a macroscale model (Fig.1(b)), which is used to analyze the buckling properties of laminates, are calculated using a mesoscale model (Fig.1(a)) which takes into account the intralaminar inhomogeneity caused by placement of the interwoven yarns and surrounding pure resin.

Figure 1: Multi-scale analysis for structural member made of woven fabric composite.

2 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

2.1 Description of material system and assumption for analysis modelling

In this study, numerical analyses and experiments, which will be described later in Sec.3, were conducted on the buckling property of plain weave fabric (CK6261C, Toray Industries, Inc.) with thermoset epoxy resin composite laminates. Carbon fiber T700S-12K was used in both warp and fill yarns in the woven fabric. The geometric dimensions of this material system, which are specified in Fig. 2, are summarized in Table 1.

When generating the finite element analysis model, the shape of the yarn cross section was assumed to be an ellipse with the major axis length d which is equivalent to the yarn width and the minor axis length t which is equivalent to half the fabric thickness. The material properties of yarns included in the cured composite laminate were assumed to be equivalent to those of a T700 unidirectional fiber reinforced composite with the fiber volume fraction of $V_f = 82.8\%$ which are presented in Table 2 as ‘Yarn’ [2]. The material properties of the pure epoxy resin which surrounds woven yarns were also shown in Table 2 as ‘Resin’ [3]. To simplify the finite element modeling, it was assumed that all the laminae included in the laminate had the same yarn direction and that the weave structures of all the laminae were aligned along the thickness direction (there was no in-plane gap of the weave pattern between all plies along the thickness direction).

Figure 2: Plain weave fabric composite.

Yarn spacing (a)	Yarn width (d)	Fabric thickness ($2t$)	Ply thickness (h)
3.37	2.94	0.5	0.5

Table 1: Geometric properties of fabric composite (unit: mm).

Yarn					Resin	
E_L [GPa]	E_T [GPa]	G_{LT} [GPa]	G_{TT} [GPa]	ν_{LT} [-]	E [GPa]	ν [-]
193	12.7	5.55	4.20	0.22	3.45	0.35

Table 2: Material properties of yarn and resin in composite [2, 3].

2.2 Mesoscale Analysis

Following the procedure proposed by Yoshida and Nakagami [1] and Yoshida et al. [2], the effective in-plane and out-of-plane elastic properties of plain weave fabric composite laminates, which included the effect of the intralaminar inhomogeneity, were calculated by using a homogenization method for calculating the equivalent plate elastic properties [4-9]. In a plain weave fabric composite, the weave pattern is repeated in the plane of the composite laminate. However, the out-of-plane periodicity (periodicity along the thickness direction) cannot be assumed because the top and bottom surfaces of the laminate are traction free surfaces. Therefore, the region that contains all of the plies is selected as a unit cell and the FE model of the unit cell is prepared as shown in Fig.3, which shows the FE analysis model of a unit cell for 3-ply laminate. After applying appropriate in-plane periodic boundary conditions to the unit cell and conducting the finite element analysis, the effective plate elastic property, which means the elastic property of the homogeneous plate that is equivalent to the fabric composite laminate, was obtained.

Figure 3: FE model for equivalent plate analysis.

Whereas, assuming the number of plies of plain-weave fabric composite to be infinite, the effective 3-D continuum elastic properties of the plain weave fabric composite was also calculated by using a homogenization procedure for calculating effective elastic properties of an equivalent 3-D continuum body [10-13]. In this case, the fabric composite has the out-of-plane periodicity (periodicity along the thickness direction) as well as the in-plane periodicity. Thus, a 1-ply region is selected as a unit cell and the finite element model as shown in Fig.4 is prepared. After applying appropriate out-of-plane as well as in-plane periodic boundary conditions to the unit cell and conducting the finite element analysis, the effective 3-D continuum elastic property, which means the elastic property of the 3-D continuum body that is equivalent to the fabric composite, was obtained.

Figure 4: FE model for equivalent 3-D continuum analysis.

One of the representative results obtained from the homogenization procedures described above is shown in Fig. 5. The apparent bending elastic modulus of laminate, which is defined later in Eq. (2), decreases as the number of laminated plies decreases. In particular, in the case of 1-ply lamina and 2-ply laminate, the bending elastic modulus significantly decreases.

Figure 5: Variation of flexural modulus with the number of plies.

2.3 Macroscale Analysis

In this subsection, the influence of the variation in the number of laminated plies on the compressive buckling characteristics of plain weave fabric composite laminates was investigated. The uniaxial compressive buckling load of the laminate was calculated using FE analysis. Fig. 6 shows the boundary

conditions for the FE analysis where upper and lower edges were clamped and both side edges were simply supported.

Figure 6: FE model for buckling analysis.

Several analysis models of fabric composite laminates with different number of plies were prepared. The elastic properties of the homogeneous plate which is equivalent to the fabric composite laminate, calculated using the procedure in Sec. 2.2 (using FE model in Fig.3), are expressed as shown in Eqs. (1)-(3) regardless of the number of laminated plies.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{12} \\ 2\varepsilon_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & 0 \\ & a_{22} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & a_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_{11} \\ N_{22} \\ N_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1^a H} & -\frac{\nu_{12}^a}{E_1^a H} & 0 \\ & \frac{1}{E_1^a H} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & \frac{1}{G_{12}^a H} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_{11} \\ N_{22} \\ N_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_{11} \\ \kappa_{12} \\ 2\kappa_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} & 0 \\ & d_{22} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & d_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M_{11} \\ M_{22} \\ M_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{12}{E_1^d H^3} & -\frac{12\nu_{12}^d}{E_1^d H^3} & 0 \\ & \frac{12}{E_1^d H^3} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & \frac{12}{G_{12}^d H^3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M_{11} \\ M_{22} \\ M_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{23} \\ \gamma_{31} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & f_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{23} \\ Q_{31} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{kG_{31}^f H} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{kG_{31}^f H} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{23} \\ Q_{31} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

In Eqs. (1)-(3), ε_{11} , ε_{22} , ε_{12} are in-plane strains, κ_{11} , κ_{22} , κ_{12} are bending/twisting curvatures and γ_{23} , γ_{31} are out-of-plane shear strains of the equivalent homogeneous plate. N_{11} , N_{22} , N_{12} are in-plane resultant forces, M_{11} , M_{22} , M_{12} are resultant moments and Q_{23} , Q_{31} are out-of-plane resultant shear forces. Components of in-plane compliance matrix $[a]$ in Eq. (1) are expressed by in-plane Young's modulus E_1^a , in-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{12}^a and in-plane shear modulus G_{12}^a as well as the laminate thickness H .

Components of out-of-plane compliance matrix $[d]$ in Eq.(2) are expressed by bending elastic modulus E^d_1 , bending curvature ratio ν^d_{12} and twisting elastic modulus G^d_{12} as well as H . Components of out-of-plane shear compliance matrix $[f]$ in Eq.(3) are expressed by the effective out-of-plane shear modulus kG^f_{31} and H . Subscripts used in Eqs(1)-(3) such as '11' of M_{11} indicate the direction based on the coordinate system shown in Fig.3. Regarding Eqs.(1)-(3), what follows should be noted; (i) The in-plane Young's modulus E^a_1 in Eq.(1) is not necessarily identical to the bending elastic modulus E^d_1 , (ii) Elastic moduli shown in Eqs.(1)-(3) such as E^a_1 vary with the number of laminated plies as shown in Sec.2 (Fig.5), (iii) Since elastic properties along the warp yarn are identical to those along the weft yarn for plain weave fabric composites, relationships such as $E^a_2 = E^a_1$, $G^f_{23} = G^f_{31}$ etc. holds.

In the buckling analysis of the fabric composite laminates, the laminate was modeled by using flat plate elements (or more precisely flat shaped shell elements). The elastic properties of a flat plate made of an orthotropic material are expressed as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{12} \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & 0 \\ & a_{22} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & a_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_{11} \\ N_{22} \\ N_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E'_1 H'} & -\frac{\nu'_{12}}{E'_1 H'} & 0 \\ & \frac{1}{E'_2 H'} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & \frac{1}{G'_{12} H'} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_{11} \\ N_{22} \\ N_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_{11} \\ \kappa_{12} \\ 2\kappa_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} & 0 \\ & d_{22} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & d_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M_{11} \\ M_{22} \\ M_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{12}{E'_1 H'^3} & -\frac{12\nu'_{12}}{E'_1 H'^3} & 0 \\ & \frac{12}{E'_2 H'^3} & 0 \\ \text{sym.} & & \frac{12}{G'_{12} H'^3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M_{11} \\ M_{22} \\ M_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{23} \\ \gamma_{31} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & f_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{23} \\ Q_{31} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{kG'_{23}H} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{kG'_{31}H} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{23} \\ Q_{31} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

In Eqs. (4)-(6), E'_1 , E'_2 are Young's moduli, ν'_{12} is Poisson's ratio and G'_{12} , G'_{23} , G'_{31} are shear moduli of the constituent orthotropic material. H' is the plate thickness and k included in Eq. (6) is the shear factor which is usually set as $k = 5/6$. It is desirable to set the elastic moduli of the equivalent homogeneous plate such as E'_1 , ν'_{12} and G'_{12} in Eqs. (4)-(6) so that the compliance matrices $[a]$, $[d]$ and $[f]$ are identical to those of the fabric composite laminate shown in Eqs. (1)-(3). However, in conventional plate elements which uses the constitutive relationships in Eqs. (4)-(6), both in-plane tensile modulus E^a_1 and bending elastic modulus E^d_1 cannot be specified by a single parameter E'_1 . Thus, the quantity H' , which originally means the actual plate thickness, is treated as an analysis input parameter. Then, the elastic moduli E'_1 etc. and H' in Eqs. (4)-(6) are set as shown in Eqs. (7)-(11) by using the elastic moduli E^a_1 , E^d_1 etc. and the actual thickness of the laminate H which are presented in Eqs. (1)-(3).

$$H' = \sqrt{\frac{E^d_1}{E^a_1}} H \quad (7)$$

$$E'_1 = E'_2 = E^a_1 \frac{H}{H'}, \quad \nu'_{12} = \nu^a_{12} \quad (8),(9)$$

$$G'_{12} = G^d_{12} \left(\frac{H}{H'}\right)^3, \quad G'_{23} = G^f_{23} = G^f_{31} \left(\frac{H}{H'}\right) \quad (10),(11)$$

It is noted that Eqs. (4)-(6) which use parameters shown in Eqs. (7)-(11) give almost the same elastic property of the composite laminate in Eqs. (1)-(3) except for the in-plane compliance a_{12} and a_{66} . Since other elastic properties E'_3 , ν'_{23} , ν'_{31} , which are required as input data in commercial software, do not affect the elastic property of plate element in Eqs. (4)-(6), these were set as follows:

$$E'_3 = E_3^{3D} \quad , \quad \nu'_{23} = \nu_{23}^{3D} \quad , \quad \nu'_{31} = \nu_{31}^{3D} \quad (12),(13),(14)$$

where quantities with a superscript 3D such as E_3^{3D} are the elastic moduli of the 3-D continuum which is equivalent to the fabric composite and they are obtained from the analysis model shown in Fig. 4.

Apart from the analysis described above, the buckling analyses of hypothetical homogeneous plates which have the 3-D continuum elastic property obtained from the analysis model shown in Fig. 4 were also conducted. In other words, analyses with the elastic property of plate elements in Eqs. (4)-(6) set as follows were conducted.

$$H' = H \quad , \quad E'_i = E_i^{3D} \quad , \quad \nu'_{ij} = \nu_{ij}^{3D} \quad , \quad G'_{ij} = G_{ij}^{3D} \quad (15),(16),(17)$$

In buckling analysis, five types of analysis models with different numbers of plies (1-ply, 2-ply, 3-ply, 4ply and 6-ply laminate) were prepared. The plate thickness H' and the elastic moduli set to the flat plate element are summarized in Table 3.

		H'	E'_1	E'_2	E'_3	ν'_{12}	ν'_{23}	ν'_{31}	G'_{12}	G'_{23}	G'_{31}
Unit	ply	mm	GPa	GPa	GPa	-	-	-	GPa	GPa	GPa
3-D continuum	1	0.5	60.59	60.59	9.58	0.10	0.43	0.07	3.68	2.59	2.59
	2	1.0									
	3	1.5									
	4	2.0									
	5	2.5									
	6	3.0									
Intralaminar inhomogeneity	1	0.3197	73.61	73.61	9.58	0.05	0.43	0.07	14.13	5.21	5.21
	2	0.9715	58.82	58.82	9.58	0.03	0.43	0.07	4.02	1.90	1.90
	3	1.5204	57.69	57.69	9.58	0.03	0.43	0.07	3.54	2.16	2.16
	4	2.0448	58.01	58.01	9.58	0.04	0.43	0.07	3.45	2.29	2.29
	5	2.5746	58.39	58.39	9.58	0.05	0.43	0.07	3.43	2.41	2.41
	6	3.0746	58.39	58.39	9.58	0.05	0.43	0.07	3.43	2.41	2.41

Table 3: Material properties and plate thickness used for finite element analysis.

3 EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF BUCKLING LOAD OF LAMINATE

Uniaxial compression buckling test was conducted for the plain weave fabric composite which was described in Sec.2.1. Specimens with the dimensions of 150mm*150mm were placed on the test fixture as shown in Fig. 7. Five types of specimen with different numbers of plies were prepared. Upper and lower edges were clamped and both side edges were simply supported. The dimensions of the test piece inside the fixture were 142 mm in width and 134 mm in height. The dimensions of the test pieces are shown in Table 4. The out-of-plane displacement (deflection) at the center of the test piece was measured by a laser displacement meter. The test load was plotted against the square of the deflection and the buckling load was calculated by the δ^2 method. Fig.8 shows the procedure to determine the buckling load P_{cr} by using experimentally obtained data.

Figure 7: Buckling test setup.

Number of plies	1	2	3	4	5
Height a [mm]	134	134.5	134	134	134
Width b [mm]	142	142.5	142	142	142
Aspect ratio a/b	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.94
Thickness t [mm]	0.499	1.02	1.55	1.98	2.51
Reference thickness [mm]	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5
Difference to reference thickness [%]	-0.2	2.0	3.3	-1.0	0.4

Table 4: Specimen dimensions.

Figure 8: Calculation method of buckling load.

4 RESULT

In the case of homogeneous flat plates which have the same in-plane dimensions and boundary conditions but the different plate thicknesses, the quantity of buckling load P_{cr} divided by the cube of the plate thickness H is almost constant regardless of the plate thickness. Thus, to evaluate the buckling load excluding the influence of the plate thickness, the quantity P'_{cr} defined in Eq. (18) is introduced.

$$P'_{cr} = P_{cr} / H^3 \quad (18)$$

Table 5 and Fig. 9 show both numerical and experimental results of P'_{cr} for the laminates with different numbers of plies. In the case of a hypothetical homogeneous plate which has elastic constants of the equivalent 3-D continuum, P'_{cr} s are almost constant regardless of the number of plies (slight variation of P'_{cr} with the number of plies in the results using equivalent 3-D continuum elastic properties may be caused by the transverse shear effect). However, if the variation of the elastic property of the laminate due to the intralaminar inhomogeneity is taken into account, P'_{cr} significantly decreases as the number of plies decreases to 1-ply. Regarding P'_{cr} calculated using elastic properties with intralaminar inhomogeneity, P'_{cr} for 1-ply lamina is 66% smaller than that for 6-ply laminate. From another point of view, in the case of 1-ply lamina, P'_{cr} calculated using elastic properties with intralaminar inhomogeneity is 66% smaller than that calculated using equivalent 3-D continuum elastic properties. Although the quantitative agreement is not good between experimental results and numerical results, experimental results also show that P'_{cr} decreases as the number of plies decreases to 1-ply. Experimental results show that P'_{cr} for 1-ply lamina is 60% smaller than that for 5-ply laminate.

Number of plies		1	2	3	4	5	6
P'_{cr}	Experiment	0.596	1.358	1.602	1.536	1.497	
	Analysis (Intralaminar inhomogeneity)	0.661	1.721	1.884	1.930		1.925
	Analysis (3-D continuum)	1.973	1.967	1.956	1.943	1.903	1.852

Table 5: P'_{cr} for laminates with different number of plies.

Figure 9: P'_{cr} vs. number of plies.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, the influence of the variation in the number of laminated plies on the compressive buckling characteristics of plain weave fabric composite laminates was investigated. The buckling analysis of the fabric composite laminate was conducted by taking into consideration the intralaminar inhomogeneity. Then, the analysis results were verified by experiments. Through numerical and experimental studies, it was found that the reduction of the apparent elastic modulus in the 1-ply lamina or 2-ply laminate can also cause a reduction of its buckling load.

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